

ELIMINATING LANGUAGE INTERFERENCE IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract.

In the process of learning any language, the student acquires the language he is learning by comparing it with his native language. When learning a foreign language, the mother tongue has a negative or positive effect, while the interaction of the studied language features with the mother tongue helps to learn the language faster, that is, it has a positive effect, while incompatible features have a negative effect on language acquisition. In this case, the positive effect of the mother tongue is called transposition, and the negative effect is called the interference phenomenon. In this study, the improvement of the mechanism of elimination of interlingual interference in general secondary school students was studied. The proposed mechanism includes organizational, educational, pedagogical and developmental stages. For each class, lesson plans were developed using inductive methods and game technologies, as well as the elimination of language interference through the electronic board. It took into account the students' language skills, native language skills and language proficiency. The teaching process was organized on the basis of internal stratification of students into groups. This mechanism was developed and tested through the form of organization of the teaching process, the mechanism was tested in grades 1-9 of secondary schools. The results were evaluated on the basis of diagnostic and formative assessment criteria, which determine the indicators of the elimination of language interference in students. Statistical analysis of the results of 4th grade students, graduates of A1 level, A2 level, 9th grade students, defined by the State Education Standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords. Interference, interlingual interference, pedagogical mechanism, multilingual environment.

Introduction. In the world, pedagogical mechanisms have been put into practice to eliminate the phenomenon of interlingual interference that occurs in the process of language learning. Attention is paid to the practical significance of expanding the pedagogical potential of the process of teaching foreign languages to language learners in leading foreign universities, the mechanisms of eliminating language interference in a multilingual environment, linguistic difficulties to determine the phenomenon of interlingual interference on the basis of comparative statistics. Due to the growing use of foreign languages in Uzbekistan, research is being conducted in pedagogical practice on ways to eliminate interference errors by analyzing the norms of proper speech organization, general and specific features of languages, internal mechanisms of each comparable language, national features. Interlingual interference, the study of linguistic, didactic, scientific-methodological and pedagogical aspects of overcoming the negative impact of the mother tongue in second

language education, taking into account the existing language experiences, especially knowledge and skills in the mother tongue, are important in learning foreign languages. In Uzbekistan, most students learn English as a foreign language. Because English is a contemporary element in the society which has become a vital instrument of communication across the world. It has made it easier for people to represent themselves in a global platform. English allows one to understand what revolves around the world because he is able to overcome barriers associated with language. Learning becomes easier because he is able to read a lot of books and articles and speak with people from different places across the world. English acts as a windowpane to the world. To be a well-informed person, it is important to learn English to overcome the many obstacles associated with lack of knowledge. (Junko Kirkpatrick 2019) Therefore, the research work is also considered in the example of English. Due to the relevance of the research, the following scientific innovations were created as a result of the work:

the negative impact of native language skills on students in the first foreign language, the positive impact of the first foreign language skills on the second foreign language in the multilingual environment was determined on the basis of optimizing the genetic properties of language (sibling and non-sister languages);

the mechanism of eliminating interlingual interference in stratified groups has been improved through the integration of collaborative and individual learning technologies;

the pedagogical possibilities of teaching English have been expanded on the basis of reducing phonetic and grammatical interference, giving priority to methodological components (identification, reproductive, creative, communicative exercises and design);

indicators of the elimination of interventional errors in the formation of skills in the types of speech activities of students in English have been improved by identifying gaps based on the criteria of formative and diagnostic assessment.

The scientific significance of the results of the study is explained by the study of the factors that cause language interference, their negative consequences, typical errors, difficulties associated with language interference in language teaching in general secondary schools and ways to improve existing opportunities identified in English curricula and textbooks.

Practical significance of the research results determined by a system of exercises and assignments based on the improvement of existing exercises aimed at preventing interference errors in the process of second language teaching, eliminating the negative effects of the mother tongue, scientific and methodological developments, improving criteria for assessing English language proficiency.

Theoretical foundations of interdisciplinary interdependence

In linguistics, the positive effect of the mother tongue on language acquisition is called transposition, and the negative effect is called the interference phenomenon. Interference is derived from the Latin "inter" - between, within, "ferentis" - transmitter, which means negative influence, obstruction, negative result in the acquisition of skills and abilities. The term was originally used in physics to refer to the increase or decrease in the amplitude of vibrations as a result of the collision of waves (Strelkov, 2005, p.488.]. Although the term interference was first used in the 19th century by Prague linguists, a group of young grammarians, Luabi noted that Weinreich's book, Linguistic Relations, became widely used only after its publication in the 20th century (2014, p. 2.). Members of the Prague School of

Linguistics have paid special attention to the place of the mother tongue in society and have identified various phenomena that prevent the rapid learning of another language in the process of learning a language. In their view, the phenomenon of interference is a state of bilingualism, that is, a departure from the norms of language in the speech of bilingual students who do not know the second language perfectly.

The emergence of a number of works in the following years devoted to the comparative study of foreign languages (Yusupov, 2007, Misirov, 2001, Kadirova 2008) shows that the phenomenon of interference is mainly studied more theoretically-typologically, and less pedagogically. In this regard, the recognition of O. Yusupov that "comprehensively studied interference aspects in comparative linguistics can be of practical importance only when studied and applied in the pedagogical plan" shows the urgency of the issue (Yusupov, 2007, p.100.). In his comparative research work on identifying differences and similarities between languages, the scholar's view that these theoretical comparisons should be considered insufficient to teach a non-native language proves the pedagogical importance of this issue. J.Buronov (1973), who created the comparative grammar of Uzbek and English, O.Azizov (1965), who developed the comparative grammar of Russian and Uzbek languages, M.Djusupov (1982), who analyzed the sound system of Russian and Kazakh languages, also studied the educational aspects of this field. The importance of development has increased.

The phenomenon of interference is the object of sociolinguistics, which is studied both pedagogically, psychologically, linguistically and methodologically. From a linguistic point of view, interference is a linguistic competence that reflects the level of mastery of the mother tongue and a foreign language, bilingualism, which is sociologically part of social culture, bilingual competencies psychologically affect the learner and the development of individual mental processes and in pedagogical education as issues of organizing the learning process in a bilingual or multilingual environment. The elimination of interference errors in a multilingual environment requires the study of these different aspects of the interference phenomenon. Since the phenomenon of interference is mainly a matter of linguistics, we first analyze its linguistic aspects.

Linguistically, the theory of interference has been extensively studied and described differently by J. Bagana (2007), T. Tsapko (2012), V. Vinogradov (1990), O. Yusupov (2007), M. Djusupov (2002) and others but problems related to interlingual interference have not yet been fully resolved.

According to V. Vinogradov, interlinguistic interference is a departure from the norms of one or each of the interacting languages, which is mainly reflected in the speech of bilingual students (1990, p.197.). A similar situation is often observed in the process of learning another foreign language by different nationalities living in our country and knowing at least two languages. According to J. Bagana, as a result of interference, a third "system" is formed in the speaker's thinking, which is a mixture of distinctive signs between a foreign and a native language (2007, p. 48.) T. Tsapko understands that "interference is the replacement of the studied language models with the corresponding elements of the native language" (2012, p. 321-326.). As a result of comparing the second language that students are learning with their own mother tongue, it is possible to observe the formation of a third trilingual system indeed.

Analyzing the interference of Russian and Kazakh languages, M. Djusupov notes that in the process of learning a second language, pronunciation and auditory perceptions of native and non-native languages complement each other, resulting in new mental forms and

stereotypes that are involuntarily realized in new speech activities (1982, p.58.). Analyzes have shown that as a result of the influence of one language on another, a phenomenon of deviation from language norms occurs during the formation and application of language devices.

The sociolinguistic essence of the process of interference is manifested in the fact that a person learning another language involuntarily translates the norms of the rules of speech, reinforced in the native language, into the language being studied (Yusupov, 2007, p.102.). In this case, it is not the emergence of internal laws of language development that matters, but the role of language in certain social contexts. Interlingual interference in the social sphere creates a bilingual environment in the coexistence of two nations in a region, longevity, immigration and intermarriage (Bagana, 2007, p. 48.).

The subject of pedagogy is interested in issues such as the possibility of acquiring specialized knowledge through foreign language interference, the extent to which bilingual or multilingualism affects the overall level of education (Zagrayevskaya, 2008, p. 5.). This, in turn, creates the need for the correct application of educational technologies in the elimination of language interference in the determination of the content of education and effective forms of organization of the teaching process in the teaching of foreign languages.

Given the psycholinguistic aspect of the phenomenon of interference, it can be noted that the manifestation of interference as a result of the activity of the speech process, its occurrence is directly related to the activity of psychophysiological mechanisms (Jumadilova & Saylaubekova, 2014, p. 94.). O. Maklakov believes that the law of general development of skills is that a person tries to fulfill a new task through the activity of previously acquired skills (2000, p. 173.). According to O. Yusupov, in psychology, "interference" is the reflection of speech components in the second process in the process of activities performed on the basis of one skill or ability (2007, p. 100). A. Carlin points out that the concept of interference is manifested in the interaction of linguistics and psychology, in psychology the object of research is mental mechanisms that can cause interference, and in linguistics the probability of violation of second language norms is understood as the object of research (1968, p. 44.)

E. Ignatev and his supporters believe that the psychological aspect of interference is the fact that the previous activity is repeated in a continuous rhythm, and as a result of its automation takes a firm place in the memory. According to them, if the next activity differs to a different extent from the previous activity, the previous activity will start to interfere with the next activity, resulting in an interference phenomenon (1970, p. 289.).

One of the most important aspects of the study of interference is the question of the communicative influence that arises in the speech process of language learners. The effect of interference can be inferred from which language group the speaker belongs to, whether it is an English-speaking community or a German-speaking community, depending on the speaker's use of language norms. The communicative study of interference allows for the prediction of errors and the identification of ways to eliminate them. A lot of sources of errors have been introduced by some innovative theorists. In the following section the primary causes of errors will be reviewed: Interlingual / Transfer errors: those attributed to the native language (NL). There are interlingual errors when the learner's L1 habits (patterns, systems or rules) interfere or prevent him/her, to some extent, from acquiring the patterns and rules of the second language (Corder, 1971). Interference (negative transfer) is the negative influence of the mother language (L1) on the performance of the target language learner (L2)

(Lado, 1964). Intralingual/Developmental errors: those due to the language being learned (TL), independent of the native language. (Farzaneh Khodabandeh, 2007, p. 113) Apparently, the definitions and views on the phenomenon of interlingual interference are different: some scholars consider interlinguistic interference to be a negative effect of language on the process of language interaction, while others interpret interpersonal interference as a transfer of speech skills to a second language. The first definition is approached linguistically, the second psychologically, which is related to the study of language as a specific system in linguistics and as a speech activity in psychology

Methods and materials

Pedagogical experiments were organized in grades 1-9 of secondary schools, where an improved mechanism for eliminating language interference developed in the research was tested. Experimental works in 2014-2015, 2015-2016, 2016-2017 academic years Tashkent city Yashnabad district 204th general secondary school, Chilanazar district 200th general secondary school, Uchtepa district 283th general secondary school, Tashkent region Qibray district 6- general secondary school, Zangiota district 14th general secondary school, Kuva district of Fergana region, Sufi village, 59th general secondary school in 3 stages.

The aim of the experiment was to test the mechanism for eliminating native language interference in language teaching.

Pedagogical experiments were organized on the basis of programs, plans, didactic requirements and principles for improving the mechanism of elimination of language interference in the process of continuing education. It was widely applied to the teaching process. During the educational process, the negative effects of the mother tongue on teaching English to students were identified and tested to increase the effectiveness of teaching. Experiments include reliance on the mother tongue to eliminate language interference, communicative orientation of education, differentiated learning, demonstration, consistency in the presentation of language material, acceleration in the teaching of a second foreign language, holistic mastery of speech activities, grammatical and phonetic was organized based on the principles of accountability and a communicative approach.

In the first stage (2019-2020 academic year) pedagogical, psychological, linguistic and didactic literature on the topic of research was studied and analyzed. Questionnaires were administered to 156 English teachers working in the pilot areas.

At this stage, experimental and control groups were formed on selected experimental sites and initial written work was obtained from students. Students in grades 2-9 will be given four speaking activities - a listening comprehension dictionary, control dictations, writing with appropriate suffixes instead of dots, composing sentences using key words, reading sentences correctly, reading and speaking a text on a given topic. speaking on the given topic, narration of the text.

Based on the given tasks, the level of phonetic and grammatical interventional errors of students was analyzed. Analysis of errors shows that phonetic and grammatical interference errors were more common in learners in language learning. Therefore, our research work aimed to work on phonetic and grammatical interference. The results of the work were examined on the example of two classes: 4th grade, which is the end of primary education, and 9th grade, which is the end of upper grades. At the beginning of the experiment, the results of the written work obtained from the 4th grade students of the secondary schools showed the following results (see Table 3.1)

Table 3.1

The initial state of occurrence of language interference in 4th grade students

Assignment type	Experimental group (181 people)			Control group (183 people)		
	High	Medium	Low	High	Medium	Low
Dictionary dictation on listening comprehension	56	55	70	57	60	64
Replace the dots with the appropriate suffixes	59	57	65	53	60	68
Correct reading of sentences	60	56	65	53	61	69
Speaking on the topic	68	60	53	58	65	62
Total:	243	228	253	221	244	261
Average:	61	57	63	55	61	65
Percentage:	34%	31%	35%	30%	33%	37%

The selection of these classes was based on the State Education Standard of Uzbekistan. Phonetic interference errors were studied mainly in 4th grade students because they were observed mainly in primary school and the State Education Standard of Uzbekistan also required correct pronunciation from primary school students, and the effects of grammatical interference were analyzed in 9th grade students. From 5th grade onwards, grammatical topics begin to be coherent, hence the grammatical interference errors of 9th grade graduates were analyzed at the request of the State Education Standard of Uzbekistan, and this situation showed the following results (see Table 3.2).

Table 3.2

The initial state of occurrence of language interference in 9th grade students

Assignment type	Experimental group (185 people)			Control group (178 people)		
	High	Medium	Low	High	Medium	Low
Control dictation on the topic	50	85	50	53	60	65
Compose and write text using key words	50	85	50	49	64	65
Expressive reading of a poem	51	84	50	49	62	67
Tell the topic	51	84	50	54	58	66
Total :	202	338	200	205	244	263
Average:	51	85	50	51	61	66
Percentage:	27%	46%	27%	29%	34%	37%

The above indicators show that students have difficulty understanding, reading, pronouncing words correctly, speaking and composing sentences and pronouncing words, and grammatically correct sentences without making mistakes in writing due to the fact that words in English are not written as they are heard and read.

The second - an improved mechanism for the elimination of language interference, developed in the research work on the basis of interventional difficulties and errors identified in the educational phase (2020-2021 academic year). To do this, the experimenter was explained how teachers could apply the mechanism to the teaching process. The content of the pedagogical process includes four aspects. Organizational aspects are organized on the basis of the teacher's activities before and during the lesson. It covers the teacher's pre-lesson activities, i.e. the preparation period for the lesson. In this case, the teacher must have the following information:

- identify the factors that cause interference;
- language experience of students, identification of existing skills and competencies;
- identify the main differences between students' language experience and the language they are learning;
- linguistic and methodological guidelines for the detection of interference errors, difficulties in accordance with the type of interference.

The use of existing opportunities in textbooks, the development of a system of special exercises and assignments on the types of linguistic interference, additional information on the use of innovative pedagogical technologies, the provision of didactic teaching aids play an important role in eliminating educational interference.

Educationally, the elimination of interlingual interference involves moral, intellectual, and aesthetic education.

Developmentally, the elimination of language interference in students involves the development of mental processes and the formation of their worldviews about cognition. Experimental trials were conducted according to the following plan (see Table 3.3).

Table 3.3.

Experimental plan

No	Experimental test content	class	hour	term
1	Unit 1. Lesson 2. "How are you?",	1	1	1 quarter
2	Unit 1. Lesson 1. "A-apricot, B-bee"	2	1	1 quarter
3	Unit 10. Lesson 2. "Trees and flowers",	3	1	3 quarter
4	"We cooked palov yesterday"	4	1	3 quarter
5.	Unit 3. Lesson 1. I live in a	5	1	1 quarter
6.	Unit 5.Lesson3. Birthday are fun!	6	1	2 quarter
7.	Unit 2. Lesson 3. "I've brushed my teeth",	7	1	1 quarter
8.	Unit 2. Lesson 3. She said she likes newspapers.	8	1	1 quarter
9.	Unit 8. Lesson 1. "We have had our house painted"	9	1	4 quarter

In this case, the experiments were conducted in one group of both parallel classes. The first group was the experimental group, the second group was the control group. Experimental trials were conducted only in the experimental groups. For example, if a school has 5 "a" and 5 "b" classes, in English they are held in one group of both classes, given that

they are divided into two groups. No experimental work is carried out in the second group, but the current control is carried out in both groups in order to compare the quality of knowledge of students in both groups. The experimental topics will be conducted on the same day as the annual plan.

Class 1. Unit 1. Lesson 2. "How are you?"

In Grade 1, students are taught how to pronounce sounds correctly. In this lesson, the reading of the letter "w", which does not exist in the Uzbek language, is explained orally and reinforced through oral exercises.

2nd grade. Unit 1. All around me. Lesson 1. A-apricot, B-bee

Students are first introduced to vowels and consonants. The letters A and B are then presented according to the plan. It is explained what sounds they are pronounced with. Reinforced with concepts of open and closed joints, they are used to provide the reading of the vowel letters A and B. The new topic is reinforced with reinforcing exercises.

3rd grade. Unit 10. Lesson 2. "Trees and flowers".

Students are shown the words sun and tulip with pictures underlining the letter. You will then be asked to find the difference between them. Once different answers are received, these sound words are repeated with all students. It is explained that the letter is pronounced as [ʌ] in the word sun and [ju] in the word tulip. The students are then told the words in which the letter is present, students are asked to listen to them and divide them into words that are pronounced with two different sounds, and the sounds are reinforced.

4th grade. "We cooked rice yesterday."

First of all, the subject of the past simple tense is presented by the inductive method. Explain how it is made and applied. The emphasis is on the pronunciation of the suffix -ed, which is added to the correct verbs in the past tense, as [t] and [d]. The game "Little Partners" will be played.

5th grade Unit 3. Lesson 1. I live in a....

Since the topic of "The present simple form of affirmation" is a grammatical material, it is advisable to spend 2 hours. In the first hour, the grammatical material is explained, and in the second lesson, the topic is reinforced with lexical material, various games, exercises, and assignments. In the first hour of the lesson, the present tense form of the present tense is taught. The new topic statement begins with a demonstration method and provides grammatical information based on the inductive method. To do this, the board or poster displays sentences in the form of modern simple sentences based on vocabulary familiar to students.

6th grade. Unit 5. Lesson 3. Birthday are fun!

This lesson explains the construction of the verbs "to be", "to have", and "to get" in the past tense. The first notions of the past simple tense in English are compared with the present simple tense in English. Concepts of horse cutting in English and Uzbek are given and reinforced on the basis of assignments.

7th grade. Unit 2. Lesson 3. "I've brushed my teeth",

It presents the present perfect tense verb. The method of presentation is carried out in an inductive way by means of dictation "Running writing". The reinforcement process is organized with the "Expand Your Speech" exercise.

8th grade. Unit 2.Lesson 3. She said she likes newspapers.

In this topic, English quotations and assimilations are explained in comparison with Uzbek. In English and Uzbek, there are differences in the use of punctuation in the transcription and assimilation of sentences. Once the topic is explained, exercises to reinforce the topic are performed.

9th grade. Unit 8. Lesson 1. "We have had our house painted"

Chapter 8 Lesson 1 introduces a device for telling someone to do something. The differences between "Have something done" and "Have done" are explained by examples. In the process of strengthening, exercises "Find the correct answer", "Translate from English to Uzbek" will be given.

It is well known that assessment criteria are a measure of a student's knowledge. This is important for every student, parent, their teacher, and the school as a whole. Students' knowledge is usually monitored on the basis of diagnostic, formative, and summative assessment types. In experimental work, we used a type of diagnostic and formative assessment. At the initial stage of assessment, a diagnostic assessment is conducted, which determines the level of knowledge, speaking skills and abilities of students in language learning, the level of mastery of the learning material. The main focus of formative assessment is to determine and monitor the relevance of students' knowledge to language learning objectives. As a result of this process, teachers routinely set lesson objectives for each class [p. 168]. Experimental exercises and assignments were identified using diagnostic and formative assessment criteria developed for four types of speech activity on the degree of elimination of language interference (see Table 3.4)

Table 3.4
Criteria for assessing the elimination of language interference

	High	Medium	Low
Listening	If the content of the given task is fully understood and phonetic and grammatical interference errors are not allowed	If the content of the given task is fully understood and phonetic and grammatical interference errors are not allowed in more than half of the task	If the content of the given task is partially understood and phonetic and grammatical interference errors are made in the half of the task
Speaking	If the words in the speech are pronounced without making phonetic and grammatical interference errors	If more than half of the sentences in the speech are pronounced with phonetic and grammatical interference errors	If half of the sentences in the speech are pronounced with phonetic and grammatical interference errors.

Reading	Completes tasks on the content of the given text, speech sounds in the language do not allow phonetic interference errors	If he / she completes more than half of the tasks on the given text content, some of the speech sounds in the language make phonetic interference errors	If half of the tasks on the given text content are completed, the speech sounds in the language make phonetic interference errors.
Writing	If the sentences do not contain grammatical interference errors	If the sentences make some grammatical interference errors	If he makes grammatical interference errors in most of the sentences.

The implementation of an improved mechanism for the elimination of language interference in experimental areas has proven its effectiveness by reducing errors in students' speaking skills. At the end of the experiment, the final control work was carried out in the 4th and 9th grades. The results were then compared with the initial condition. The work performed showed the following results (see Tables 3.5 and 3.6).

Table 3.5

Overall results at the end of the experiment on the degree of elimination of language interference in 4th grade students

Criteria	Experimental group (181 people)			Control group (183 people)		
	High	Medium	High	Medium	High	Medium
If the content of the given task is fully understood and the task does not contain phonetic and grammatical interference errors	62	94	25	25	80	78
If the words in the speech are pronounced without making phonetic and grammatical interference errors	63	95	23	31	76	76
Completes tasks on the content of the given text, speech sounds in the language do not allow phonetic interference errors	63	93	25	28	78	77
If the sentences do not contain grammatical interference errors	63	94	24	27	79	77
Total:	251	376	98	111	313	308
Average:	63	94	24	28	78	77
Percentage:	35%	52%	13%	15%	43%	42%

Table 3.6

Overall results at the end of the experiment on the degree of elimination of language interference in 9th grade students

Criteria	Experimental group (186 people)			Control group (178 people)		
	High	Medium		High	Medium	
If the content of the given task is fully understood and the task does not contain phonetic and grammatical interference errors	45	126	15	18	82	78
If the words in the speech are pronounced without making phonetic and grammatical interference errors	46	128	12	25	77	76
Completes tasks on the content of the given text, speech sounds in the language do not allow phonetic interference errors	48	124	14	22	79	77
If the sentences do not contain grammatical interference errors	46	126	14	21	80	77
Total:	185	504	55	86	318	308
Average:	46	126	14	22	79	77
Percentage:	25%	68%	7%	12%	44%	44%

In the third confirmation phase (2021-2022 academic year), the indicators of the results obtained in the educational phase were summarized and a mathematical-statistical analysis was performed to determine the percentages of effectiveness.

Findings and discussion

The organization of experimental work in a certain order and on the basis of the program ensured the effectiveness of this process, and the level of elimination of language interference by students was determined. In the dissertation the criteria of "high", "medium", "low" levels of efficiency of improvement of students on elimination of language interference are specified. (See Table 3.7).

Table 3.7

General results of the level of elimination of language interference in 4th and 9th grade students

The time of the experiment	Grades	Number of pupils	Levels of mastery		
			High	Medium	Low

At the beginning of the experiment	4 th grade	Experiment	181	61	34%	57	31%	63	35%
		Control	183	55	30%	61	33%	65	37%
At the end of the experiment		Experiment	181	63	35%	94	52%	24	13%
		Control	183	28	15%	78	43%	77	42%
At the beginning of the experiment	9 th grade	Experiment	185	51	28%	86	46%	48	26%
		Control	178	51	29%	61	34%	66	37%
At the end of the experiment		Experiment	186	46	25%	126	68%	14	7%
		Control	178	22	12%	79	44%	77	44%

The results of pedagogical experiments were compared and the results of the experimental groups were shown to be satisfactory.

Experiment with the results of experimental work performed

Based on the data obtained from the results, the statistical analysis was developed on the basis of the Xi-square () criterion. The results of the experiments allowed to determine the level of reduction of interference errors in the 4th and 9th grades of secondary schools using an improved mechanism for the elimination of language interference. Statistical analysis of the data obtained from the experimental results was carried out on the Xi-square () criterion acoc and the following results were obtained. Since the experimental results were based on 3 types of assessments in the selected control and experimental group students, C = 3, a = 0.05, n = 3 - 1 = 2, Tkr = 5,991 obtained from the table G of the Xi-square criterion .

At the beginning of the experiment, the null hypothesis is accepted because the mastery levels of the 4th pupil were Tkuz = 0.18 < Tkr = 5.991 according to the hijab. We perform calculations based on the formula: n₁ = 181, n₂ = 183, C = 3.

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n_2} \sum_{i=1}^3 n_{2i} x_i = \frac{1}{181} (63 \times 3 + 57 \times 4 + 61 \times 5) =$$

$$= \frac{1}{181} (189 + 228 + 305) = \frac{722}{181} = 3,98$$

$$y = \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{i=1}^3 n_{1i} y_i = \frac{1}{183} (65 \times 3 + 61 \times 4 + 55 \times 5) =$$

$$= \frac{1}{183} (195 + 244 + 275) = \frac{714}{183} = 3,90$$

$$\bar{x} = 3,98 > 3,90 = \bar{y}$$

At the beginning of the experiment, the level of mastery of 9th grade students gave the following indicators. n₁ = 185, n₂ = 178, C = 3.

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n_2} \sum_{i=1}^3 n_{2i} x_i = \frac{1}{185} (48 \times 3 + 86 \times 4 + 51 \times 5) =$$

$$= \frac{1}{185} (144 + 344 + 255) = \frac{743}{185} = 4,01$$

$$y = \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{i=1}^3 n_{1i} y_i = \frac{1}{178} (66 \times 3 + 61 \times 4 + 51 \times 5) =$$

$$= \frac{1}{178} (198 + 244 + 255) = \frac{697}{178} = 3,91$$

$$\bar{x} = 4,01 > 3,91 = \bar{y}$$

The knowledge levels of the students in the selected groups did not differ significantly at the beginning of the experiment. Therefore, the experimental and control groups were selected correctly.

Now the quality in the experimental group at the end of the experiment in 4th grade we show that the index is higher than that of the control group. To do this, we find the average of the scores in the experimental and control groups, - the average of the scores in the experimental group, - the average of the scores in the control group.

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n_2} \sum_{i=1}^3 n_{2i} x_i = \frac{1}{181} (24 \times 3 + 94 \times 4 + 63 \times 5) =$$

$$= \frac{1}{181} (72 + 376 + 315) = \frac{763}{181} = 4,21$$

$$y = \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{i=1}^3 n_{1i} y_i = \frac{1}{183} (77 \times 3 + 78 \times 4 + 28 \times 5) =$$

$$= \frac{1}{183} (231 + 312 + 140) = \frac{683}{183} = 3,73$$

$$\bar{x} = 4,21 > 3,73 = \bar{y}$$

As a result of mathematical-statistical analysis, it was found that the average score in the experimental group in Grade 4 was 11% higher than the average score in the experimental group compared to the control group. This research has proven to be effective.

In Grade 9, we determine the average of the scores in the experimental and control groups to determine how well the quality indicator in the experimental group is relative to the control group. In this case - the average value of points in the experimental group, - the average value of points in the control group.

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{i=1}^3 n_{1i} x_i = \frac{1}{186} (14 \times 3 + 126 \times 4 + 46 \times 5) =$$

$$= \frac{1}{186} (42 + 504 + 230) = \frac{776}{186} = 4,17$$

$$\bar{y} = \frac{1}{n_2} \sum_{i=1}^3 n_{2i} y_i = \frac{1}{178} (77 \times 3 + 79 \times 4 + 22 \times 5) =$$

$$= \frac{1}{178} (231 + 316 + 110) = \frac{657}{178} = 3,69$$

$$\bar{x} = 4,17 > 3,69 = \bar{y}$$

It can be seen that the average score in the experimental group in Grade 9 was found to be 10% higher than in the control group, and research has proven to be effective.

Thus, the statistical analysis showed the effectiveness of experimental work to determine the degree of formation of an improved mechanism for the elimination of language interference in language teaching in general secondary schools.

Conclusion

1. Interlinguistic interference is a phenomenon of negative impact of existing language experiences on students' native language on the studied language, and this phenomenon, which belongs mainly to the field of linguistics, is also studied in pedagogy, psychology, sociology and methodology. The elimination of interlingual interference in pedagogy was carried out on the basis of pedagogical principles and laws.
2. In secondary school students, interlingual interference is often observed at the phonetic and grammatical levels of language, and interventional errors are manifested in direct connection with these types of interference. This analysis of errors resulting from grammatical and phonetic interference has shown that there is a socio-pedagogical need to study interference errors and their causes and to further improve textbooks.
3. In today's multilingual environment in our country, interventional difficulties depend on how many language experiences students have, and the greatest difficulty occurs through the negative impact of the student's native language. The stronger the differences and distinctions between the mother tongue and the language being studied, the stronger the effect of the interference. In the course of the research, it was proved that the skills acquired through the first foreign language will help to learn the next languages easily.
4. Mistakes that can occur due to native language interference in textbooks, and the lack of ways to overcome them, create serious difficulties in language teaching. Integrating foreign language lessons with native language lessons, using existing opportunities to prevent interference errors, will help students to master the language quickly, easily and thoroughly.
5. The results of the survey showed that foreign language teachers are not familiar with the content and theoretical aspects of the phenomenon of language interference, exercises and tasks aimed at eliminating interference errors, do not systematically use innovative technologies. A comparative study of the differences between students' language and mother tongue, the use of their language experience, a system of exercises aimed at eliminating language interference, the use of innovative technologies have shown effective results in the elimination of interlingual interference in secondary schools.
6. The pedagogical mechanism of language interference elimination developed in the course of research work helps teachers to systematically organize their activities in this area on an integral and continuous basis, to identify the factors that cause interference, to effectively use language experience and opportunities in textbooks.
7. The organization of language lessons on the basis of differentiated educational technology and differentiated assessment of the degree of elimination of interventional errors in students strengthens the creative motivation of students, ensures transparency and objectivity. The effective use of didactic games and electronic whiteboards in the classroom stimulates interest, research and activity in students.
8. The results of experimental testing of the mechanism for the elimination of interlingual interference developed in the course of the research showed that the efficiency of the experimental groups increased by 11% in 4th grade and 10% in 9th grade.

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